

20. Initial approach to monitoring reporting and verification (MRV) of agroforestry carbon farming in the EU.

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EURAF is based in Montpellier, Brussels & Toledo (Transparency Register ID of [913270437706-82](https://ec.europa.eu/transparency/transregister/details/913270437706-82)). It aims “to promote the adoption of agroforestry practices across Europe and support awareness, education, research, policy and investments which foster the use of trees on farms”. It has a network of 31 affiliated entities in 23 countries. Other EURAF Policy Briefings are listed [here](#). Contact: policy@euraf.net

Abstract

Policy Briefing #20 (v5) updates the previous version (25.8.25) in response to the DGCLIMA public consultation on the draft Carbon Farming Delegated Act ([22.1.26 - 19.2.26](#)).

Comments are provided on definitions, scope, baselines, additionality, sustainability, monitoring tools, permanence, and geospatial coordinates of agroforestry. A standard typology of 8 agroforestry and 30 carbon-farming practices is given.

We welcome re-wording of the “tree planting” methodology as “afforestation”, since this will avoid confusion with agroforestry.

It is important that CRCF methodologies match those used by Member States in their annual reporting of greenhouse gas emissions to the UNFCCC, and use the most accurate parcel-based reporting possible. The Commission is therefore asked to urge Member States to meet their commitments to provide open access to anonymised IACS geospatial information on agricultural parcels and land use, and in particular to comply with the open API requirements of the High Values Dataset Implementing Regulation (2023).

Member States should also move their GHG reporting to true “wall to wall” identification of both agricultural and forestry parcels: facilitating future exchange of information between LULUCF and CRCF carbon farming reporting.

1. Introduction

Version 5 of PB#20 responds to the Commission's consultation on the draft CRCF Delegated Act ([Ares \(2026\)746080](#)) “Establishing the Certification Methodologies for Carbon Farming Activities” (22/1/2026 - 19/2/2026). The draft Act has developed three methodologies: a) “Agriculture and agroforestry on mineral soils”, b) “Rewetting of peatlands” and c) “Afforestation”. We are particularly pleased that the provisional title of the third methodology was changed from “tree planting”. Our recommendations follow the main sections of the Delegated Act.

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2. Definitions.

In Section 0

In addition to the 11 definitions given, we suggest the following:

- A. “**Agroforestry**” means the intentional integration of trees and agriculture on the same land. Member States have different approaches to recording agroforestry parcels using land-use codes or flags in their national LPIS/GSAA systems. Where these approaches are incomplete, it is proposed that agricultural parcels with a Copernicus Tree Cover Density greater than or equal to 5% should be considered as “agroforestry”. This is justified because 5% is the threshold used by the FAO for “Other Wooded Land”.
- B. “**Landscape Features**” means hedgerows, individual or groups of trees, tree rows, field margins, patches, buffer strips, ditches, streams, small ponds, small wetlands, stonewalls, cairns, terraces, cultural features as defined in CAP Implementing Regulation (L/458/463) Article 3.1(a).
- C. “**Forest**” means blocks of trees exceeding the national thresholds for minimum area, tree crown cover and tree height set by Member States in Annex II of the EU LULUCF Regulation (2018/841), as amended by Regulation 2023/839.

3. Activity, Monitoring and Certification Periods

In Section 1.2 (Activity period, monitoring period and certification period)

- D. The draft Delegated Act indicates that the activity period for agroforestry (i.e. the time during which certified units can be generated) should be set at 30 years, in two 15-year stages, with an additional monitoring period of at least 10 years after the activity ends. Agroforestry is the intentional integration of trees with agricultural crops (such as tree crops and herbaceous crops) and, where possible, livestock grazing within a single production system. These practices can evolve over time and may involve a succession from arable crops to pasture, allowing livestock grazing when the tree canopy has become wide. The maximum mean annual increment for most agroforestry plantations will peak at more than 30 years, and the proportion of higher diameter-timber assortments will be at a maximum even later. Therefore, we suggest a more flexible approach: **whereby carbon removals and GHG reductions are calculated and monitored for up to 60 years.**

In Section 1.3 (Planning and Reporting)

- E. Monitoring reports and reverification audits should be produced **at the end of 5-year periods.**² Operators can decide at the end of each period, whether to continue under the existing carbon scheme or transition to a new, potentially higher-impact variant. An opportunity should also exist to modify the monitoring plan for the future 5-year periods, as methodologies and available data improves.
- F. The location of agroforestry parcels should, wherever possible, be **validated using CAP LPIS and GSAA datasets**, complemented by inclusion of: a) small agricultural areas which are outside formal CAP IACS systems, and b) parcels of forest land. Already, those forest parcels which receive CAP (or equivalent) grants are included in the LPIS systems of all member states, so this extension should be feasible.
- G. The DGCLIMA geospatial CRCF registry of parcels should therefore be based as closely as possible on the CAP LPIS/GSAA databases provided under the terms of the EU High Value Datasets Regulation (q.v.) **and also used for LULUCF reporting by Member States.**

4. Scope

In Section 2.1 (Scope)

- H. $\text{GHG}_{\text{Associated}}$ for agriculture and agroforestry includes direct N_2O emissions (and indirect volatilisation of ammonia³ and emissions from leached nitrates, **but not yet CH_4** (Table 3 in the Delegated Act). This is an omission, particularly for agroforestry since the impact of trees is generally to strengthen the soil methane

² The EU DigitAF project has produced a tools, projects and data catalogue to assist with the MRV of agroforestry projects ([link](#))

³ Bealey WJ, Dore AJ, Dragosits U, Reis S, Reay DS, Sutton MA. The potential for tree planting strategies to reduce local and regional ecosystem impacts of agricultural ammonia emissions. *J Environ Manage.* 2016;165: 106–116. doi:10.1016/j.jenvman.2015.09.012

sink through improved diffusivity, reduced compaction and greater aeration associated with soil drying (Priano et al. 2017; Gauthier et al. 2016).⁴

- I. Section 2.2.1 (d2) refers to “an increase in direct and indirect N₂O emissions from agricultural soils resulting from changes in the application of fertilising products” but does not mention the frequently observed **decrease in direct N₂O emissions caused by agroforestry**.⁵
- J. Documentation should include an **extended list of carbon farming practices for all three methodologies**. EURAF [Research Report #11](#) gives a “Standard list of Carbon Farming Practices” for potential reference in the CRCF Annex to the Delegated Act. This is based on proposals in a range of recent projects and consultancy reports, including the DGCLIMA carbon farming Technical Guidance Handbook ([DGCLIMA 2021](#)) and the JRC “Classification Scheme Based on Farming Practices” ([JRC 2024](#)). This typology includes the 10 agroforestry practices (Table 1) which have been recognised by EURAF since [Policy Briefing #1](#).
- K. In addition to tree-planting in agroforestry systems it is hoped that “**assisted natural regeneration**” of silvopastoral agroforestry can be included in the “agriculture and agroforestry” methodology. Degraded parklands are extremely common in southern Europe and their inclusion in carbon farming certification will greatly encourage their regeneration.
- L. We propose a typology of 8 types of agroforestry on agricultural lands (Table 1).

Table 1: EURAF Typology of Agroforestry Practices (EURAF [Policy Briefing #1](#)). See also Table 2 for the suggested standard typology of 30 carbon farming practices.

Tree location	Agroforestry System	Agroforestry Practice	
		Agricultural Land	Forest Land
<i>Trees inside parcels</i>	Silvopastoral agroforestry	1 Wood pasture	10 Forest grazing
	Silvoarable agroforestry	2 Alley cropping 3 Alley coppice 4 Food forests	4 Food forests
	Permanent crop agroforestry	5 Orchard cropping 6 Orchard grazing	
	Agro-silvo-pasture	7 Agro-silvo-pasture	
<i>Trees between parcels</i>	Tree Landscape Features (protected by CAP Conditionality Rules)	8 Woody-landscape-features	
<i>Trees in settlements</i>	Urban agroforestry	9. Settlement agroforestry	

5. Baselines

In Section 2.3 (Baselines)

- M. We recognise the difficulties in adopting the “**standardised baseline**” MRV approach and the need to use a “*project-based*” accounting system in the first version of the Delegated Act. However, we note that the CAP LPIS/GSAA geospatial recording system has been used by Member States since 1992, and that most MS should be able to provide evidence of afforestation and agroforestation⁶ at least from 2007. In the next iteration of the Delegated Act it is recommended that inclusion of carbon farming by early adopters be explored.
- N. For standardised baselines to work, and also for the proposed Sustainability Compass, Land Registry, and Union Carbon Removals Registry, it is vital to have access to LPIS/GSAA information for both agricultural and forestry parcels. The **EU High Value Dataset Implementing Regulation (2023)** required all Member

⁴ An exception to this rule applies in wooded wetlands where the stems of trees may open channels in the soil for increased methane emission (Pangala et al. 2013).

⁵ Gross CD, Bork EW, Carlyle CN, Chang SX. Agroforestry perennials reduce nitrous oxide emissions and their live and dead trees increase ecosystem carbon storage. *Glob Chang Biol.* 2022;28: 5956–5972. doi:10.1111/gcb.16322

⁶ Planting or enhanced natural regeneration of formally mapped areas of agroforestry

States to make this data available in API format by June 2024. It recommended that DGCONNECT issue a “letter of formal notice” to the **7 countries** which are still not compliant.⁷

- O. April 2027 is the 20th Anniversary of the **EU INSPIRE Directive**, requiring open access to geospatial data collected with public funds. It is recommended that the EU celebrates entry into force of the INSPIRE Directive with an "Open Data Day" on 14th May 2027 and that this could be a good date to launch the DGCLIMA CRCF Registry.

6. Quantification and monitoring approaches

In Section 2.4 (Quantification and monitoring approaches)

- P. The "**minimum accuracy**" requirement for models (2.4.1.1) of 90% of observed values falling within the model's 90% confidence interval will be difficult to deliver for agroforestry biophysical models, given the difficulty of calibrating different mixtures of tree and crop species in a range of biophysical conditions. This is particularly the case for below-ground biomass. This accuracy is possible for tried and tested models of agricultural monocultures, but it is unrealistic for agroforestry.

7. Additionality

In Section 3.1 (Regulatory test)

- Q. Regulatory test - protection of existing woody landscape features is required under GAEC⁸ but it no longer obliges farmers to establish new features to reach a threshold coverage, hence **there is no contradiction with the regulatory test for agroforestry**. The draft text should make this clear.

In Section 3.2 (Financial viability)

- R. The **financial viability incentive effect test** requires the operator to submit cost or investment comparison models which demonstrate that carbon farming is not economically viable for farmers or forest owners without the long-term security of certified carbon payments after initial CAP establishment payments have ended. This provision is very welcome: in the CAP 2014-2022 only 5 kha of agroforestry was established in the whole of the EU, despite MS planning for 80 kha. It is clear that agroforestry is currently not sufficiently attractive to farmers, without the additional incentive of carbon farming payments. Recent [techno-economic evidence](#) developed within the Carbon Farming MED project reinforces this conclusion, demonstrating through farm-level modelling that carbon farming only becomes financially viable when long-term, certified carbon payments complement CAP start-up support. EURAF ([3.4.2025](#)) has proposed that CAP ecoschemes (baselining), investment and AECM measures can be considered as a “starter pack” prior to the adoption of successfully established agroforestry plantations into certified schemes.
- S. **Derogation from the financial viability incentive effect test** for operators who started agroforestry activities between 2023 and 2027 is welcome, since they cannot be expected to perform this test retrospectively. Also, the growth of trees during the first five years of a widely-spaced plantation is extremely slow, and very little sequestration will have taken place since 2023.
- T. **Group certification**. We welcome the opportunity for operator-groups to jointly handle internal management, monitoring standards, external audit, liability and eligibility, and urge the Commission to disseminate good practice developed by these groups. Ultimately carbon farming must extend to millions of hectares and this could be the first step to including agriculture and forestry in the EU Emission Trading Scheme.

8. Storage, Monitoring and Liability

In Section 4.1 (Risk assessment)

⁷The HVD Regulation (2023) obliged Member States to provide LPIS/GSAA data by June 2024 meeting 6 criteria: i) free of charge, ii) under a permissive open licence (Creative Commons BY 4.0 or equivalent), iii) in machine-readable formats, accessible via both iv) Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) and v) bulk download, and vi) be up to date. Data availability has improved recently but 5 countries (BG, HU, CY, EL, MT) are 100% in breach, and DE and IT fail to provide information for the majority of their regions (EURAF [Research Report #8v2](#)).

⁸ CAP Good Agricultural and Environmental Condition (GAEC) 8 ensures that hedges, ponds, trees etc which are noted in IACS spatial records as “landscape features” should be protected by farmers. GAECs are being replaced by “Farm Stewardship” in the CAP after 2028, with a reduced and nationally-determined level of statutory regulation.

- U. The Delegated Act indicates that **the risk of tree species choice and the risk of reversal of management practices** should be assessed by operators at the beginning of the activity period and at the end of the monitoring period (Section 4.1.3). This will not be easy and we welcome the JRC’s provision of a dataset⁹ on current and future species suitability, and that Table 7 shows the risks associated with agroforestry to be lower than those in conventional forestry. EURAF has provided comparisons of the comparative risks for agroforestry versus forest plantations in areas of [windthrow](#), [wildfire](#), and [pests](#), which confirm the lower level of risk expected for agroforestry.
- V. **The risk of reversal** will be reduced if tree rows in agroforestry are registered in the LPIS/GSAA systems of Member States. These will have a status similar to “landscape features” in most Member States and will be protected in a similar way to areas of forest. This “*guarantee of permanence*” may be reflected in lower reversal risk premia.

9. Sustainability

In Section 5.1 (Minimum sustainability requirements)

- W. Regarding the **minimum sustainability requirements**, EURAF has published Policy Briefings on the minimum requirements in the 6 areas of sustainability described in the EU Sustainability Taxonomy Regulation ([2020/852](#)),¹⁰ and in its Climate Delegated Act ([2021/2139](#)) and Environment Delegated Act ([2023/2486](#)). We welcome that the CRCF has used the same framework to assess minimum requirements as these regulations, and urge DGFISMA to continue its previous work on the assessment of agricultural sustainability in the EU Taxonomy Regulation.

In Section 5.2 (Cobenefits for biodiversity and ecosystems)

- X. Regarding co-benefits for the protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystems, **EURAF has published Policy Briefing #66 with recommendations for monitoring and a review of existing literature**. We welcome that the Commission and JRC have created an evidence library on the environmental impacts of different farming practices,¹¹ including agroforestry, and that connections are made with existing environmental directives and regulations¹². The indicators of forest biodiversity included in Section 5.3.4.f (copied from Annex III of the Nature Restoration Regulation) are not universally appropriate throughout Europe. In particular, high levels of “standing deadwood” and “lying deadwood” will increase the susceptibility of forests to wildfires, pest attack, and windthrow. High levels of “forest connectivity” will increase the spread of wildfires. We recommend mosaic landscapes of forest, agroforestry and agriculture to mitigate these risks.

10. References

- Gauthier, Mathieu, Robert Bradley, Sebastien F. Lange, Suzanne Edith Allaire, William F. J. Parsons, and Mario Alberto Cuellar Castillo. 2016. “Tree-Based Intercropping May Reduce, While Fertilizer Nitrate May Increase, Soil Methane Emissions.” *Canadian Journal of Soil Science*, nos. CJSS-2016-0085 (December). <https://doi.org/10.1139/cjss-2016-0085>.
- Pangala, Sunitha R., Sam Moore, Edward R. C. Hornibrook, and Vincent Gauci. 2013. “Trees Are Major Conduits for Methane Egress from Tropical Forested Wetlands.” *The New Phytologist* 197 (2): 524–531. <https://doi.org/10.1111/nph.12031>.
- Priano, M. E., V. S. Fusé, S. Mestelan, et al. 2017. “Afforested Sites in a Temperate Grassland Region: Influence on Soil Properties and Methane Uptake.” *Agroforestry Systems* 92 (2): 311–320. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10457-017-0104-7>.

⁹ Carbon removals and carbon farming risk assessment and buffer pool datasets for forests ([CF-RISK-EU](#)) - although this is currently available only for 35km hexagons.

¹⁰ EURAF Policy Briefings are available for the impact of agroforestry on climate-mitigation ([#26](#)), climate-adaptation ([#27](#)), water-resources ([#64](#)), water-pollution ([#65](#)), biodiversity ([#66](#)) and the circular-economy ([#67](#)).

¹¹ JRC evidence library on farming practices ([link](#))

¹² Directive 2009/147/EC (Birds), Directive 92/43/EEC34 (Habitats) and the Regulation 2024/1991 (Nature Restoration)

11. Relevant EURAF Policy Briefings

- [#1](#) Agroforestry and the Green Deal (v115.9.20)
- [#8](#) Agroforestry for carbon farming in the EU - history and policies (v4 1.4.24)
- [#15](#) Monitoring trees outside forests in the EU (v4-7.1.24)
- [#17](#) Agroforestry in the revised LULUCF Regulation (v4 30.6.24)
- [#19](#) Agroforestry and the EU ABER Regulation (v1 31.12.22)
- [#20](#) Agroforestry and the draft Framework Regulation for Carbon Removals (v1 31.12.22)
- [#21](#) Landscape Features in the new CAP (v1 30.1.23)
- [#24](#) Agroforestry and Parliament’s report on Sustainable Carbon Cycles (v1 5.3.23)
- [#26](#) Agroforestry and the 2040 AFOLU net-zero target (v1 23.6.23)
- [#27](#) Agroforestry and adaptation to climate change (v1 31.7.23)
- [#28](#) Agroforestry and the EU Sustainable Finance Initiative (v1 15.12.23)
- [#64](#) Agroforestry for carbon farming - water resources (draft)
- [#65](#) Agroforestry for carbon farming - control of water pollution (draft)
- [#66](#) Agroforestry for carbon farming - biodiversity and the protection of ecosystems
- [#67](#) Agroforestry for carbon farming - the circular bioeconomy (draft)
- [#68](#) Availability and use of IACS geospatial data in the EU
- [#69](#) Governance and performance of the CAP, the role of agroforestry
- [#70](#) Agroforestry and simplification of the CAP

<p><i>This Policy Briefing is a joint output from two projects: the DigitAF Project. Grant agreement: 101059794, which aims to develop digital tools to boost Agroforestry in Europe to meet climate, biodiversity and sustainable farming goals. and the Carbon Farming Med Project, (Interreg EURO-Med), which focuses on regenerative agricultural practices and creating a carbon credits market to support EU climate neutrality goals by enhancing CO2 capture and aiding environmental restoration. Views and opinions expressed are those of the authors only</i></p>	
<p>Co-funded by the European Union</p>	

Table 2 - EURAF Typology of Carbon Farming Practices, including agroforestry and those agricultural practices which can be used in crop alleys alongside the agroforestry tree rows - covered by “stacking” of CAP establishment interventions and subsequent CRCF MRV methods. (please comment on [spreadsheets](https://tinyurl.com/yc2ejvpu))
<https://tinyurl.com/yc2ejvpu>

Category	#No	Practice	Brief summary	Land Use (LULUCF)	STACK with AF?
A. Annual crops, permanent crops and silvoarable systems	1	Conservation Tillage (Reduced/No-Till)	Minimising or eliminating mechanical soil disturbance (ploughing) to reduce soil erosion, improve water infiltration, and protect soil structure and organic matter from oxidation. Covered by Verra IALM	Annual and perennial crops	(yes)
	2	Catch/Cover Crops	Cover/catch crops (e.g. legumes, grasses) during fallow periods keep the soil covered, increase biomass input, prevent nutrient leaching, and suppress weeds. In perennial crops they are also important for reducing erosion. Covered by Verra IALM methodology.	Annual and perennial crops	yes
	3	Crop residue retention and mulching	Mulching with crop residues can increase SOM, lower soil temperature, retain moisture and suppress weeds. Covered by Verra IALM	Annual and perennial crops	yes
	4	Improved crop rotations and diversification	Alternating different crop species on the same plot over sequential seasons, including deep-rooting crops and legumes, to break pest cycles, improve nutrient cycling, and enhance below-ground biomass. Covered by Verra IALM.	Annual crops	yes
	5	Improved/precision fertiliser management	Precision application of fertilisers to match crop needs, reducing overuse and cutting emissions of nitrous oxide (N ₂ O), a potent GHG. VERRA has a proposed methodology for precision fertilisation and irrigation for GHG reduction.	Annual and perennial crops	yes
	6	Biochar application on soils	Amending soil with biochar, a stable, charcoal-like material produced from biomass pyrolysis. It provides a highly durable form of carbon storage in soil. VERRA has a methodology for biochar utilisation in soils and non-soil applications.	Annual and perennial crops	yes
	7	Herbaceous perennial crops & filter strips	Cultivating perennial crops, including for biomass/energy (e.g. Miscanthus, willow), which reduce soil disturbance and build larger, deeper root systems compared to annuals, leading to higher SOC sequestration.	Annual and perennial crops	yes
	8	Short rotation coppicing and woody filter strips	Short rotation coppice is explicitly classified as an agricultural crop in the CAP SP Regulation and the Renewable Energy Directive. It therefore falls within the scope of the CRCF.	Perennial crops	yes
	9	Herbaceous Intercropping	Intercropping with legumes can reduce N ₂ O emissions and enhance SOC sequestration. It also leads to reduced fertiliser use and derived emissions.	Perennial crops	yes
	10	Alley cropping	Trees planted in widely spaced rows (1-3 m wide) have crop alleys between them – whose width is usually set to match available machinery. Tree rows often contain shrubs or wildflowers to increase biodiversity in the system.	Agroforestry	yes
	11	Alley coppice	A new version of an old system called "coppice with standards", where a few isolated trees or rows of trees are retained as an upper strata for timber or other products.	Agroforestry	yes
	12	Food forests	A sustainable multi-layered system of edible plants designed to mimic the structure and natural function of a forest. It is usually managed on a very small scale.	Agroforestry	yes
	13	Intercropping in permanent crops	Permanent crops in the EU are orchards, olive groves, vineyards and (sometimes) plantations of chestnuts and cork oak. They can be intercropped for additional income and diversity.	Agroforestry	yes
	14	Grazing in permanent crops	As above, but with grazing.	Agroforestry	yes

B. Grasslands, silvo- pastoral systems and animal husbandry	15	Managed/rotational Grazing	Controlling the timing, intensity, and duration of livestock grazing to allow for pasture recovery, which can enhance root growth and soil organic carbon.	Grassland	yes
	16	Conversion of cropland to permanent pasture	Converting annual cropland to permanent pasture or meadow, a land-use change that leads to significant and continuous accumulation of soil organic carbon over decades.	Cropland, Grassland	yes
	17	Wood pasture	Planting, regenerating and managing trees on permanent grassland at densities or with block sizes, which do not meet the national definitions of "forest land".	Agroforestry	yes
	18	Diets for methane reduction	Various strategies to reduce emissions – including increasing digestibility, lignin content, fat content, additives, and precision feeding. One option is mixing tree leaves into ruminant diets.	Animal husbandry	yes
	19	Biochar in animal husbandry	Biochar incorporated in animal feed or bedding to reduce emissions.	Animal husbandry	yes
	20	Improved manure storage	Processes, which reduce the emission of N ₂ O and CH ₄ from stored manure and slurry.	Animal husbandry	no
C. Forestry	21	Afforestation & reforestation (AR)	Establishing new forests on land that was not recently forested (e.g., abandoned cropland) or restoring degraded forests. Sequesters large amounts of carbon in woody biomass and soil. Presumably includes rewilding projects ?? Afforestation involves a change in land use.	Cropland, Grassland	no
	22	Improved Forest Management (IFM)	Adopting silvicultural practices that increase the carbon stock within existing forests, such as delaying harvesting, avoiding clear-cutting, and diversifying tree species to enhance resilience.	Forest	no
	23	Forest grazing (FG)	Grazing used for fire control in dry periods and also for shelter in winter and shade in summer. This would not be a permanent land use, but animals would come and go as required. Electric collars are sometimes used to control movements.	Forest	yes
D. Organic Soils and Wetlands	24	Peatland rewetting & restoration (PWR)	Raising the water table on drained organic soils (peatlands) to halt the rapid oxidation of peat, thereby preventing massive CO ₂ emissions and restoring the habitat's function as a carbon sink.	Cropland, grassland, forest, wetland	no
	25	Paludiculture	"Wet farming" on rewetted peatlands, involves the cultivation of wetland-adapted crops (e.g., reeds, cattails) for biomass or other products, allowing for economic use while keeping the soil water saturated.	Cropland, grassland, forest, wetland	yes
E. Mixed systems	26	Agro-silvo-pasture	Mixtures in time of silvoarable and silvopastoral systems, e.g. when trees become too dense to allow annual cropping.	Agroforestry	yes
	27	Landscape features (woody, wet, herbaceous)	Landscape features are protected in CAP Legislation and have targets set nationally in the NRR. Woody landscape features (copses, hedges, lines of trees and isolated trees) are a form of agroforestry.	Agroforestry	yes
	28	Enhanced rock weathering	Involves spreading of crushed silicate rock (e.g. basalt) on cropland or grassland to react with rain and CO ₂ to form stable bicarbonate ions.	Cropland, grassland	yes
	29	Organic Amendments	Application of organic materials such as animal manure, compost, or digestate from biogas production directly to soils. May involve Nitrates Directive application thresholds.	Cropland, grassland	yes
F. Settle- ments	30	Tree planting and management in settlements	Planting and maintaining trees on land defined in LULUF as "settlement" rather than "forest". Urban forestry sensu lato.	Settlements	no